

EBFMC25-IP-07 · Family Medicine as the Cornerstone of a Sustainable Healthcare System: Opportunities, Challenges, and the Path Forward

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Family medicine (FM) plays a pivotal role in delivering accessible, holistic, and cost-effective healthcare.

Main Discussion: This paper explores the current and potential contributions of family medicine to sustainable healthcare systems, drawing from international literature, OECD and WHO reports, and recent research.

Conclusion: It highlights the benefits of strong primary care models, outlines existing challenges -such as physician burnout and technological integration- and proposes strategies to reinforce the field for future demands.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Family medicine, primary care, health equity, digital health, chronic disease, sustainability

INTRODUCTION

In 2016, WONCA developed a document establishing standards for family doctors to ensure the global consistency of their work and to continuously improve our profession based on scientific principles (WONCA, 2018). The most recent definition of FM dates from 2018 and is known as the Göktaş definition: "General practitioners/family physicians are specialist doctors trained in the principles of the discipline. They are personal doctors who take primary responsibility for providing comprehensive and continuing care to every individual seeking medical attention, regardless of age, gender, or illness. They care for individuals in the context of their family, their community, and their culture, always respecting the autonomy of their patients. They are aware of their professional responsibility to the community as well. When discussing and formulating treatment plans with their patients, they consider physical, psychological, social, cultural, and existential factors and use the knowledge and trust built through repeated contacts. General practitioners/family physicians fulfill their professional role by promoting health, preventing disease, providing cure, care, or palliation, and by encouraging patient empowerment and self-management" (Goktas, 2025).

WHAT CHARACTERIZES A FAMILY PHYSICIAN/GENERAL PRACTITIONER?

A family physician or general practitioner is distinguished by a diverse set of competencies and skills that merge humanistic and medical attributes. These professionals embody a multidimensional role within the healthcare system, requiring a balance of technical expertise, emotional intelligence, and adaptability (World Health Organization [WHO], 2025; "ZGP_04_2023_Allgemeinmedizin", 2023).

A family physician should:

1. Remain faithful to the fundamental principles of medicine - which include helping individuals, providing hope, offering healing where possible, and delivering ongoing support in all circumstances.

2. Commit to scientific medicine, maintaining a broad base of evidence-based knowledge and applying it effectively in clinical practice.
3. Perceive patients as individuals, engaging meaningfully with their personal stories, respecting their diversity, and accompanying them through various stages of life.
4. Be capable of discovering the unknown, functioning much like a detective - synthesizing diverse pieces of information and skillfully managing diagnostic uncertainty.
5. Acknowledge the uniqueness and individuality of every patient, ensuring that care is tailored and personalized.
6. Accept human and medical limitations, recognizing that not all conditions are curable and that compassion and presence are essential aspects of care.
7. Fulfill multiple roles within the healthcare system, including those of clarifier, coordinator, diagnostician, mediator, and healer.

Family medicine lies at the heart of primary healthcare (PHC) and is increasingly seen as a foundation for sustainable, equitable, and effective health systems. The World Health Organization and OECD have emphasized PHC's transformative role in improving healthcare delivery across socioeconomic lines (OECD, 2020; World Health Organization [WHO], 2025). As healthcare systems globally seek to balance rising demand with limited resources, FM offers a cost-effective and person-centered model that adapts to patients' needs throughout the life course. One defining strength of FM is its contextual and holistic nature. Physicians do not treat isolated diseases but consider the patient's environment, family dynamics, and social realities (Kato, 2022). This depth of understanding builds stronger therapeutic relationships and ensures continuity of care, particularly beneficial in chronic disease management and preventive services (Gaglioti et al., 2023). A recent study underscores this approach's financial and clinical value—highlighting that primary care visits in the U.S. Veterans Health Administration led to significant per-patient cost savings, especially for high-risk individuals (Gao et al., 2022). An interesting conclusion was drawn by researchers studying productivity and continuity of care in family medicine. Their data indicate that the productivity benefits of care continuity are especially pronounced among older patients, those with multiple chronic conditions, and individuals with mental health disorders. Moreover, strong family medicine systems promote health equity. In rural or underserved areas, family physicians often represent the only consistent point of care (Kajaria-Montag et al., 2024; Piccoliori et al., 2023). Their presence helps mitigate disparities in healthcare access and outcomes, ensuring that marginalized populations receive necessary treatment (Chang et al., 2017). Similar conclusions were reached by Turkish researchers who evaluated the impact of family medicine centers on the care of pregnant women and infants (Aygün, 2021). The importance of these centers was particularly evident in provinces where fewer specialists were available (Aygün, 2021). The advantages of FM are clearly demonstrated in European countries with well-established primary health care (PHC) systems, where rates of preventable hospital admissions are significantly lower. As Quaglio and co-authors state in their research on the EU health system, the future of healthcare will depend on a stronger role for primary care (Quaglio et al., 2018). This includes a clearer shift from care-oriented models to those focused on health promotion and prevention, a deep commitment to good governance—particularly through stakeholder participation—and the systematic reuse of data to build health data-driven learning and healthcare systems. As expressed by van Weel and co-authors in their study, the goals of primary health care closely align with those of universal health coverage, which aims to ensure access to essential health services, as well as safe, effective, and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all individuals (van Weel & Kidd, 2018). Furthermore, findings from a study published in *The Lancet* emphasize that prioritizing the prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases, alongside the strengthening of health systems, remains critically important—particularly if we aim to improve healthy life expectancy (HALE) in the future (GBD 2021 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators, 2024).

Another important topic in healthcare is climate protection. As Schmiemann and colleagues stated in their article, climate protection also constitutes health protection, and many climate protection measures have a direct positive impact on the health of citizens (Schmiemann & Dörks, 2022).

Yet family medicine faces profound challenges. Physician burnout, driven by emotional stress and administrative burdens, remains pervasive. Reports from both U.S. and European contexts document alarming levels of exhaustion among family doctors, calling for targeted interventions to support mental health and professional satisfaction (Hoff et al., 2024; Rochfort et al., 2021; Soler et al., 2008). Simultaneously, the

growing prevalence of chronic illnesses places mounting pressure on already strained systems (Martin, 2007). Family medicine must evolve to meet this demand, integrating its principles into broader systemic reforms (Brailard et al., 2018). Technological transformation presents both opportunity and disruption. The advent of digital health tools, AI-driven decision support systems, and telemedicine can enhance care delivery but require substantial adaptation (Radionova et al., 2023; Schütze et al., 2023; Weik et al., 2024). Successful implementation hinges on thoughtful design, practitioner involvement, and adequate training. Interprofessional collaboration is also critical (Rawlinson et al., 2021). When family physicians work closely with nurses, specialists, and allied health professionals, patient outcomes improve. However, structural barriers—such as role ambiguity and fragmented communication—must be addressed to enable such teamwork (Arenson & Brandt, 2021; Rawlinson et al., 2021). Looking ahead, several strategic reforms are essential. Medical education must integrate family medicine from the earliest stages, fostering interest and competence through mentorship and longitudinal clerkships (van Weel & Kassai, 2017). Flexible work models can help retain a diverse workforce by accommodating different life paths, including those of women and academic practitioners. Additionally, reducing bureaucratic load via optimized electronic health records and task delegation to non-physician staff will allow doctors to focus on patient care (Drummond et al., 2012; Ma & Zhao, 2023; Neves & Burgers, 2022)).

CONCLUSION

Family medicine is not just a discipline; it is a gateway to more humane, responsive, and sustainable healthcare. Its ability to adapt to patient needs, reduce healthcare costs, and foster health equity underscores its foundational role in primary care. However, to meet future challenges, it requires strategic investments in education, workforce flexibility, digital infrastructure, and interprofessional collaboration. By reaffirming and strengthening the role of family physicians, health systems can build greater resilience and ensure better outcomes for all. Family medicine is not just a discipline; it is a gateway to more humane, responsive, and sustainable healthcare. Its ability to adapt to patient needs, reduce healthcare costs, and foster health equity underscores its foundational role in primary care. However, to meet future challenges, it requires strategic investments in education, workforce flexibility, digital infrastructure, and interprofessional collaboration. By reaffirming and strengthening the role of family physicians, health systems can build greater resilience and ensure better outcomes for all.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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